

Scaling Quantum Circuit Simulation: Optimizations for the FTDD Framework

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Resumen— Classical simulation remains essential for the development of quantum algorithms; however, traditional matrix-based methods struggle with scalability. While the Fast Tensor Decision Diagram (FTDD) framework offers a hybrid approach by combining the strengths of Tensor Networks and Decision Diagrams (DDs) for memory-efficient simulation, its core operations are often bottlenecked by memory management structures. Our primary motivation is to address the high computational and spatial cost associated with the hash tables, as well as to simplify the complexity of the simulation workflow. This work introduces systematic, low-level optimizations to the framework. Our main contribution is the enhancement of the memory management layer for the internal tables. We implemented a node reuse mechanism and designed a controlled strategy for hash table growth. These improvements minimize the memory footprint and reduce the costly hashing overhead inherent in DD-based simulators. We performed a thorough experimental analysis using a diverse set of quantum circuits, which were characterized by well-established metrics. Experimental results demonstrate that our enhancements improve the tool's performance and scalability. Notably, these advancements enable the simulation of complex circuits, such as Quantum Fourier Transform, with hundreds of qubits, on a standard server with 2-Tb of memory.

Palabras clave— Quantum Computing Simulation, Decision Diagrams, Tensor Network, Statevector Simulation.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE field of Quantum Computing (QC) has attracted attention due to its transformative potential in various fields [1]. However, the capabilities of current quantum devices are limited by the constraints of the Noisy Intermediate-Scale Quantum (NISQ) era [2]. That includes a restricted number of qubits and susceptibility to noise. These factors hinder the reliable execution of advanced quantum algorithms. Consequently, classical simulators are indispensable for designing, validating and optimising quantum algorithms. However, traditional simulation approaches based on matrix and vector multiplications face severe scalability challenges due to the exponential increase in computational and memory requirements [3]. It is important to emphasise that the fundamental factor limiting the size of quantum circuits that can be simulated on classical hardware is memory rather than time or the raw computational capabilities of modern supercomputers.

To address the limitations of circuit simulation, several methodologies have been introduced, including full wavefunction evolution [4] and Tensor Network (TN) [5]. The last one has demonstrated remarkable efficacy in simulating random quantum circuits [6].

However, their efficiency is strongly dependant on the order the tensors are contracted. Finding the optimal order is an NP-hard problem [7], so it is important to develop heuristics to efficiently approximate the optimal order.

Alternative ways of representing, storing and manipulating states and operations have been proposed, such as Decision Diagrams (DDs) [8]. This type of structure was designed to enhance the efficiency of quantum operations by minimising memory usage. This is achieved by exploiting mathematical properties to reduce data storage and avoiding their repetition of equivalent operations [9]. The prevailing state-of-the-art tool is known as DDSIM [10] and has shown to be competitive with matrices.

In this study, we use FTDD [11], a tool that combines TNs and DDs in a unique way, making use of the strengths of each. This hybrid approach establishes FTDD as a highly promising framework with the potential to rival well-established simulators such as DDSIM (DD-based) and GTN [12] (matrix-based). This DD-based tool relies on two hash tables (`UniqueTable` and `ComputeTable`) to take advantage of their benefits. While the implementation of these structures is crucial for the sequential performance of the tool, several studies indicate that these global tables often act as a significant barrier to parallelization, limiting the scalability of DD-based structures in high-performance environments [13]. This work aims to optimize the implementation of these tables to enhance the tool's performance by enabling the simulation of larger circuits and reducing computational time [14].

We extend the functionality of the FTDD framework by introducing a unified simulation interface that standardises the execution workflow and abstracts internal complexities from the user. In addition, the management of the `UniqueTable` and `ComputeTable` has been substantially improved through two core enhancements: preventing the premature deletion of nodes that remain in use, and enabling the safe reuse of nodes marked as dead by the garbage collector, thereby reducing memory overhead. We further introduce a heuristic that regulates the size of both tables to mitigate uncontrolled growth as circuit size increases. Beyond these architectural improvements, we conduct an extensive experimental evaluation using a diverse benchmark suite comprising some of the most widely studied circuits in the literature, such as RQC, QFT, QPE, QNN, QWalk, GHZ, and Graph states. This allows us to analyse the behaviour of the tool across markedly different circuit families. Our results de-

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monstrate that FTDD can simulate a broad range of circuits at sizes significantly larger than those achievable with matrix-based tools such as GTN. In particular, FTDD is capable of simulating QFT circuits with more than 120 qubits on a machine with 2 TB of memory, clearly surpassing the limits reported for tools such as DDSIM and GTN.

The paper is structured as follows: Section II briefly reviews some related work. Section III summarizes the theoretical background of our work, including basic aspects of quantum computation, tensor networks, decision diagrams, and hash tables. Section IV provides definitions of metrics that will be used to characterise and select the set of quantum circuits to be used. In section V, we detail the improvements that have been made to enhance the tool's performance. In section VI, we provide a detailed description of the experiments conducted and discuss the results. Finally, Section VII presents the conclusions and suggests directions for future research.

II. RELATED WORK

There exists a wide variety of quantum simulators that operate both sequentially and in parallel [15], and most of them are based on the evolution of the full quantum state using matrices. Nevertheless, the exponential increase in spatial and temporal costs associated with simulation means that the number of qubits is limited to a few tens, even in the most powerful supercomputer available [16].

The use of TN for simulating quantum circuits was firstly proposed by Markov and Shi [17], which led to the development of quantum simulators based on this idea, like QTensor [18]. But the performance of this kind of simulators strongly depends of the order in which the contractions are made. One of the most widely used tools for this purpose is `cotengra` [19], which besides tree decompositions, also implements more sophisticated optimization techniques such as heuristic cost models, hyper-graph partitioning, and stochastic or evolutionary search methods. `cotengra` can yield contraction orders close to the optimal when enough time is given. The problem with these simulators based on matrix representation of the information is that, even with the final tensors, the dimensions of the matrices grows exponentially with the number of qubits, which is a major constraint, especially in terms of space cost. To assess this problem, other representations of the information have been proposed.

DDs were adopted to represent data and operations for various applications, due to their ability to reduce both temporal and spatial costs. In [20], the authors provide the first description of how Binary Decision Diagrams (BDDs) should be implemented. This article laid the foundations for the development of various types of DDs with diverse applications [21,22]. In [23] the first attempt can be found to use this representation to simulate quantum circuits. Since then, many tools have been developed using this type of diagrams. The most well-known library

is MQT [10], which is utilised for both simulating and verifying quantum circuits. This tool uses Quantum Multiple-Valued Decision Diagram (QMDD) as their representation, a variant of the DDs designed specifically for quantum circuits [10]. QMDD partitions a transformation matrix into four sub-matrices of equal size. These sub-matrices are then partitioned in a similar way until the matrix's dimension is 1×1 . This method of representing matrices is somewhat rigid as it does not allow for a different order of variables. To address this limitation, Tensor Decision Diagrams (TDDs) were introduced to combine the best features of DDs and TNs [24].

III. BACKGROUND

This section provides a brief overview of the fundamental theoretical aspects. For an in-depth analysis of QC, readers are directed to consult [25] or [26].

A. Quantum Circuits as TNs

Similar to the classical bit, the basic unit of information in QC is the qubit, which can be written as a linear combination of two basic states as $\alpha |0\rangle + \beta |1\rangle$ with $\alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{C}$ [27]. A quantum system is formed by a set of n qubits, ϕ_1, \dots, ϕ_n . This constitutes a Hilbert space of dimension 2^n , whose basic states are in $\{0, 1\}^n$. Therefore, the state of a quantum system $|\psi\rangle$ can be described as:

$$|\psi\rangle = \sum_{i \in \{0,1\}^n} \alpha_i |i\rangle \text{ with } \forall i \in \{0,1\}^n, \alpha_i \in \mathbb{C}, \quad (1)$$

where the probability of measuring $|i\rangle$ is given by $|\alpha_i|^2$. Quantum systems are manipulated through quantum operators that are unitary matrices of dimension $2^n \times 2^n$. Typically, these operators only act on a subset of the system's qubits. Quantum circuits are commonly used to represent the successive application of quantum operators g_1, \dots, g_k . Quantum algorithms can be represented by a quantum circuit, and have an associate unitary operator that represents their complete functionality.

Tensors are a natural generalisation of matrices. A tensor of rank r is defined as an element $d_1 \times \dots \times d_r$ existing in the space $\mathbb{C}^{d_1, \dots, d_r}$. A complex value can be seen as a tensor of rank 0, while a vector is a tensor of rank 1. Similarly, a matrix of dimension $n \times m$ is a tensor of rank 2. Tensors have a defined set of operations, including the tensor product, trace, contraction, and partitioning [28]. One of the most significant operations is the contraction. Contraction of two tensors $R_{x,z}$ and $S_{y,z}$ is a tensor obtained by summing up over the shared indices, defined as follows:

$$T_{x,y} = \sum_{z \in \{0,1\}} R_{x,z} \cdot S_{y,z} \quad (2)$$

In general, the successive contraction between pairs of tensors of a network allows to obtain a single tensor representing its full functionality. The quantum state $|\psi\rangle$ can also be represented as a vector

$|\psi\rangle = [\alpha_0, \alpha_1]^T$, where $\alpha_0, \alpha_1 \in \mathbb{C}$. Therefore, it can be represented as a rank 1 tensor T_q . Similarly, the operators associated with the gates applied to a single qubit can be represented as rank 2 tensors T_{q_1, q_2} . In general, a gate acting on n qubits can be represented as a tensor of rank $2n$.

A quantum circuit can be modeled as a TN, where each gate is represented as a tensor. Consequently, since the behavior of a quantum circuit can be simulated using the matrix representing its functionality, it can similarly be simulated using its tensor representation. This implies that simulating a quantum circuit is equivalent to contracting its associated TN. This principle underpins the approach proposed by Markov and Shi to reduce the cost of simulating quantum circuits [17].

B. Decision Diagrams

Quantum circuits are usually implemented by using matrices, whose main advantage is the availability of efficient algorithms for matrix multiplication. But this is not the only type of structure that we can use. DDs are acyclic undirected graphs that represent the gates that compose the circuits and the unitary matrices used during its processing (simulation, verification, etc).

Two main data structures are usually employed to efficiently store the DDs. On the one hand, the `UniqueTable` stores the information about the graph nodes and on the other hand, the `ComputeTable` stores the operations as they are performed. This implementation is advantageous due to the operations on tree-like DDs are usually performed recursively based on the subtrees of each node [24]. If an operation between subtrees has already been performed, it is retrieved directly from the compute table.

Tensors can also be represented as a DDs using TDD [24], which allows the benefits of both techniques in the handling of quantum circuits. In order to achieve this objective, a number of methods have been developed that are essential for DDs to be able to work with TNs, including the contraction operation.

TDDs use nodes to represent the indices of TN, with each one having two successors linked by edges. One of the successors is associated with the value 0 of the node, while the other successor is associated with the value 1. Each edge has a weight indicating the value by which the TDD must be multiplied. In the graphical representation, the absence of a weight on the edge indicates that its weight is 1. The TDDs introduced in [24] were implemented in Python. The improved C++ version, designated Fast Tensor Decision Diagram (FTDD), will be employed [11]. In this new version, the authors make improvements to the TDD which includes Edge-centric Data Structures for TDD, employment of Key BDD Optimizations [20] or the execution of Near-Optimal Contraction Order (`cotengra` in this case), with which the authors can obtain speedups up to 175x respect to the Python version.

C. Hash Tables

A hash table is a data structure designed to store and retrieve (key, value) pairs with an average-time complexity of $O(1)$ for lookup, insertion, and deletion operations [29]. They have become a ubiquitous component in high-performance software, including compilers, interpreters, symbolic manipulation tools, and, most notably, DD packages used in formal verification and symbolic simulation. Its efficiency relies on the use of a hash function, which maps an arbitrary key to an index in an underlying array (bucket), combined with a collision-resolution strategy to handle cases where multiple keys map to the same bucket. This design enables significantly faster access times than classical search structures such as linked lists. FTDDs are derived from BDD, and the general architecture used to implement BDD use two hash tables in his core [20], which fulfill distinct but complementary roles:

1. `UniqueTable`: enforces the canonicity of the decision diagram. Typically indexed by the tuple describing a node (key, childs) and ensures that only one node with a given structure exists. This mechanism is critical for reducing the storage cost.
2. `ComputeTable`: functions as a memorization cache for intermediate computation results and stores entries indexed by the operation and its operands. This avoids redundant work and is essential for performance when executing complex or deeply nested operations on decision diagrams.

IV. BENCHMARKS AND METRICS

In order to evaluate the performance of the simulators, it is imperative to employ a set of metrics and quantum circuits that are both relevant and well-established. As was the case in [30], the present study will rely on a list of metrics that characterise the topological nature of static quantum circuits. These metrics will be used to select quantum circuits that differ in their topologies. We will use them to select a total of eight circuits from MQTBench [31]. This yields a test suite that is representative of practical quantum-computing applications.

First, we use metrics to characterise the structural properties of the circuits analysed in this work. We consider: the *Effort* (E) metric [32], which captures the structural complexity of the circuit; the *Entanglement Ratio* (ER), *Critical Depth* (Cd), *Parallelism* (Pa), and *Program Communication* (Pc) metrics from SupermarQ [33], which quantify the density of two-qubit interactions, serial bottlenecks, parallel structure, and communication patterns among qubits, respectively; and the *Entanglement Variance* (EV) from QASMBench [34], which measures how uniformly entanglement is distributed.

The benchmark suite employed in this study comprises a broad and heterogeneous collection of circuits, selected to span a wide variety of structural

behaviours according to the metrics above. These include several of the most representative and widely studied circuits in the quantum-simulation literature, such as QFT, QPE, RQC, GHZ, QNN, QWalk, RA and Graph. Together, they cover many of the key algorithmic families used in practice and in benchmarking frameworks. This diversity is essential for assessing the robustness of the simulator across different topological characteristics, rather than for a narrow or specially favourable subset of circuits. Figure 1 shows the evolution of the effort with the number of qubits for each circuit.

Fig. 1: Evolution of the Effort metric with respect to the number of qubits for each of the circuits.

V. FTDD OPTIMIZATION

In a previous work [35], FTDDs were tested across a broad variety of quantum circuits and contraction-order selection methods. That revealed several implementation issues, along with functional and performance limitations that affected the robustness and scalability of the tool. The present work analyzes the results of an improved version of FTDD that addresses these limitations, correcting identified errors, and improving performance, particularly with respect to the memory cost of TN contractions.

In this section, we describe the implementation details of the revised version. Firstly, several previously undetected issues had hindered the correct construction and manipulation of the underlying TN components. In particular, recurrent errors in the detection and propagation of open indices led to malformed intermediate representations, compromising the reliability. These issues have now been corrected: open indices are consistently recognised, validated, and updated throughout all stages of the FTDD pipeline, ensuring stable behaviour.

We also have introduced a new high-level simulation function designed to streamline and standardize the execution of quantum-circuit simulations within the FTDD framework. Previously, users were required to manually invoke a sequence of low-level operations (ranging from the initialization of the tool to circuit preprocessing and TN construction to contract the network), making the simulation workflow prone to inconsistencies and difficult to reproduce. The newly implemented function encapsulates this complexity by enforcing a canonical order of operations and abstracting internal procedural details. This not only reduces user-side overhead but also en-

sures methodological uniformity. As a result, FTDD now offers a clearer and more robust user interface, further strengthening its value as a practical simulation tool.

Additionally, we revised the behaviour of the two core data structures that underpin the FTDD representation, namely the `ComputeTable` and the `UniqueTable`, in order to improve memory usage and reduce unnecessary resource consumption. First, the `ComputeTable` has been updated to ensure that nodes currently referenced during intermediate computations cannot be prematurely deleted. In the previous implementation, the garbage collector could remove nodes that were still in active use, potentially leading to invalid pointer accesses or inconsistencies in the DD layer. The updated mechanism introduces explicit reference tracking, preventing the garbage collector from reclaiming nodes whose lifecycle is tied to active entries.

Second, modifications to `UniqueTable` now allow nodes that have been marked as dead to be safely reused. Earlier versions relied on a one-use lifecycle for `UniqueTable` entries, resulting in unnecessary memory pressure when large numbers of short-lived nodes were created during highly entangled simulations. The new reuse strategy enables the system to repurpose entries that are no longer semantically active, thereby reducing allocations, and improving the overall memory footprint of the simulator. Together, these enhancements strengthen the efficiency and reliability of the FTDD memory-management model, particularly for large-scale simulations where node growth is a critical performance factor.

Finally, we redesigned the sizing policy of the `UniqueTable` and `ComputeTable` to address the exponential memory growth that previously occurred. In the original FTDD version, allocated memory size of the `UniqueTable` depended exponentially of the number of qubits, and the `ComputeTable` was setted into a fixed value of 2^{15} buckets. This behaviour often led to excessive and unpredictable memory usage, making simulations infeasible for circuits of even moderate size. To overcome this limitation, we now enforce a constant memory footprint for both tables by constraining their combined capacity to a fixed and small fraction of the available memory.

The hash function employed is a 32-bit FNV scheme. Prior work has shown that table sizes of the form $2^x - 1$ yield particularly robust distribution properties for this type of hash function [36]. For this reason, we introduce a parameter N that determines the number of buckets assigned to each table: the `UniqueTable` is allocated with $2^N - 1$ buckets, while the `ComputeTable` is assigned $2^{N-1} - 1$ buckets. The value of N is chosen so that the combined memory footprint of all tables accounts for approximately 10% of the total system memory. The decision to adopt this sizing strategy arises from extensive empirical analysis indicating that table-growth patterns vary significantly across circuit families. Consequently, no single static configuration provides con-

sistently optimal behaviour for all benchmarks. In particular, increasing the size of the `ComputeTable` is essential for storing a sufficiently large number of intermediate operations, thereby enabling the detection of repeated computations. At the same time, the table must remain small enough to ensure that node removal can occur effectively and that memory usage does not become intractable. The selected configuration provides a practical balance between these competing requirements.

By tying the table sizes to a fixed portion of system memory, FTDD adapts automatically to the available memory while ensuring controlled memory usage. This dynamic, resource-aware allocation strategy markedly improves scalability and prevents the runaway table expansion that previously hindered large-scale simulations. Although this approach introduces a minor drawback—namely, that the tables retain a fixed and relatively large size even for small circuits, thereby reserving more memory than strictly necessary, its practical impact is limited. Small circuits do not come close to exhausting available memory, and the allocation of larger tables does not noticeably increase contraction time when memory-reservation overhead is taken into account. More importantly, the primary aim of this work is to ensure spatial efficiency for large-scale simulations, where memory is the dominant bottleneck. In this context, the advantages of the new sizing policy decisively outweigh the overhead incurred for small circuits, and the overall behaviour of FTDD becomes significantly more robust and scalable.

VI. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

This section presents the methodology used to conduct the experiments, together with the resulting data and its analysis. Our objective is to compare the spatial and temporal costs of our enhanced FTDD implementation with those of the previous version, as well as with GTN, a well-established framework that realizes TN through matrix representations.

A. Experimental Environment and Methodology

All experiments have been run on a single node including 2 Xeon 6418H with 24 cores each, 2Tb of RAM and 4 GPU H100-80Gb. The operating system used was Linux 5.4.0-72-generic 80-Ubuntu. Two types of experiments were conducted. First, a small set of circuits was used to evaluate the improvements of the latest FTDD version (section VI-B). Subsequently, all circuits described in Section IV were employed to perform a comparative analysis between the FTDD and GTN tools (section VI-C).

Unless noted otherwise, all experiments used the same workflow. All simulations were performed using statevector evaluation, meaning that the input was fixed (in our case, to state $|0\rangle$) and the output remained open. Two contraction plans were used: the plan obtained with the `sequential` method (selected for its simplicity and because it is known to be among the least effective orders for statevector simulation

with DDs) and the plan obtained with the `cotengra` method, one of the best-known optimization strategies. No prior pre-processing was applied. `cotengra` had one hour to compute the order with the `minimize` parameter set to `combo` with 56 threads. All simulations have a time constraint of one hour to perform the simulation. They started with circuit with the smallest number of qubits and continued with larger ones until the tool could no longer complete the simulation due to memory or time constraints.

B. Evaluation of Memory Optimization Strategies

In this section, we evaluate the efficiency of the improvements with respect to the original version. We employ the `sequential` method in conjunction with three representative circuits that highlight the variability. Regarding the versions under consideration, we denote the original FTDD implementation as `original`, the one that incorporates only the mechanism for correctly deleting nodes and reusing it as `Node-Reuse (NR)`, and the version with all modifications as `Node-Reuse and Table-Resize (NRTR)`. For each version, we evaluate both execution time and memory consumption, which was measured using the python function `psutil.virtual_memory`.

An examination of the memory usage presented in Figure 2 reveals two clear patterns. First, the `NR` configuration consistently exhibits lower memory consumption than the `original` implementation in all scenarios, highlighting the benefits of explicitly deleting and reusing nodes correctly. The second pattern concerns the comparatively high memory usage observed for the `NRTR` version across all circuits at smaller sizes. This behavior arises from its use of fixed-size tables: regardless of how few nodes are stored, the memory allocated for these tables imposes a substantial lower bound on overall memory consumption. As the number of qubits increases, this difference gradually decreases, as the table sizes required by the other implementations progressively approach those of the `NRTR` version. It is also important to note that not all circuits reach the same number of qubits (particularly in the QNN and RQC cases) because each simulation was executed only up to the point at which either the one-hour time limit or the available system memory (2 Tb) was exceeded.

The advantages of fixing the table size become especially evident in the case of the QFT circuit. In the figure 2, both the `original` and `NR` configurations exhibit exponential growth, whereas the `NRTR` version shows no increase in memory consumption. Starting at approximately 25 qubits, the number of nodes required by the simulation grows only marginally; the exponential behaviour observed in the other versions is therefore attributable to the growth of the tables themselves rather than to the memory needed to represent intermediate contraction results. Our experiments were terminated at 120 qubits due to the lack of larger benchmark circuits, but the memory profile of the `NRTR` version shows no indication of significant growth beyond this point.

Fig. 2: Evolution of the memory usage of the original, NR and NRTR versions of the FTDD with the `sequential` method.

Fig. 3: Evolution of the Contraction time of the original, NR and NRTR versions of the FTDD with the `sequential` method.

An analysis of the execution times in logarithmic scale presented in Figure 3, reveals a consistent pattern. Notably, the behaviour of the algorithms varies significantly depending on the type of circuit, which also influences the relative performance of the three versions evaluated. In general, the `original` version exhibits lower runtime than the NR implementation. This difference arises from the additional overhead associated with maintaining the status of each node. The NRTR version almost always shows better performance than the NR version. This improvement is attributable to the increased size of the `ComputeTable` structures, which, being larger, can store more intermediate results and thereby reduce the number of repeated operations performed. However, this benefit is not sufficient to compensate fully for the additional bookkeeping overhead, and the execution times of the NRTR version remain, in most cases, higher than those of the `original` version. Nevertheless, the average observed difference in runtime is below 5%.

C. Comparing DD and Matrix-based simulation

The objective of this section is to compare the performance of FTDDs (using the NRTR version), in terms of both execution time and memory consumption, with that of a well-established tool for matrix-based TN simulations, GTN. All circuits were execu-

ted following the procedure described above, with the exception of QPE, QNN and QWalk, for which a longer time limit of 10 hours was imposed. This adjustment was necessary because these circuits exhibit significantly higher runtime compared to the others, while both GTN and FTDD showed modest memory usage under the one-hour limit. Extending the time window therefore enabled a more informative analysis of their memory behaviour.

In Figure 4, the memory usage of both tools is presented, in which can be seen a large variety of behaviour across the tools and contractions methods. It is important to highlight that FTDD exhibits relatively high memory usage even for small circuits. Recall that this behaviour originates from the fixed size of its internal tables, which imposes a constant minimum memory overhead, as previously noted. Based on the observed performance, two groups of circuits can be identified based on their performance. The first group corresponds to the circuits QFT, Graph, GHZ and QPE. In this group, FTDD's memory consumption avoids the exponential growth observed for GTN. FTDD's memory usage appears to stabilise for all circuits in this group except QPE, whose memory behaviour is notably irregular as the number of qubits increases.

The second group includes the RQC, QNN,

QWalk, and RA circuits, within which two distinct cases arise. For QWalk, the limiting factor for FTDD was execution time, whereas for GTN it was memory usage. Thus, although GTN may perform better for small qubit counts, FTDD would be able to simulate larger circuits in the absence of time constraints. In contrast, for RQC, QNN and RA, GTN consistently achieves better memory performance than FTDD.

In Figure 5, the execution times of each circuit across the different tools and methods are shown. As anticipated from the diversity of circuits selected through the topological metrics, the behaviour of the tools varies substantially across the circuits, making it difficult to identify large groups of circuits with similar performance profiles. Nevertheless, two distinct groups emerge based on the relative performance of FTDD compared to GTN. The first group includes the QFT, Graph, and GHZ circuits, which is almost the same first group as in the memory analysis, with the exception of QPE. In this group FTDD does not exhibit exponential growth in simulation time. For QFT, the execution time grows exponentially up to 23 qubits and then stabilizes around 80 seconds, remaining nearly constant as the number of qubits increases. The time does not stabilize for Graph and GHZ. In this group, FTDD clearly outperforms GTN, which cannot simulate circuits beyond 40 qubits due to insufficient memory, whereas FTDD handles the maximum number of qubits available in the MQT test suite.

The second group consists of the RQC, QNN, QWalk, QPE, and RA circuits. In this group, both FTDD and GTN exhibit exponential growth in execution time. Within it, three cases can be identified. The first includes the QNN and RA circuits, for which the increase in execution time is exponential and stable for both tools, and where the best ordering for GTN is able to simulate consistently larger circuits than the best ordering for FTDD. The second case corresponds to the QPE and QWalk circuits, where both tools show comparable performance, reaching approximately the same number of qubits. Finally, the third case comprises the RQC circuits, for which execution times increase in a similar way than QWalk and QPE, but where GTN achieves a better performance than FTDD.

Finally, it is worth examining the influence of the two contraction-ordering strategies employed throughout the experiments. The behaviour of the `sequential` and `cotengra` ordering differs markedly across both tools and circuit families. In general, `cotengra` could not simulate circuits as big as the `sequential` method, due to the lack of memory to calculate the path. For instance, with FTDD simulating QNN, `cotengra` gives best results but stops at 16 qubits while `sequential` can simulate up to 24 qubits. For FTDD, `cotengra` often yields faster simulations for a fixed circuit size; however, this tendency is far from uniform. In circuits such as QFT, RA, or QPE, the `sequential` method achieves lower execution times for GTN, which may be partly

explained by the limited one-hour time budget available for `cotengra` to compute the contraction plan, but also could be explained for `cotengra` not optimizing the time, but instead optimizing both memory and time. In contrast, `cotengra` with FTDD performs better than `sequential` in general in the cases where there is enough memory to get a plan. That means that `cotengra` is giving a path that can effectively reduce the size of the DDs used during the contraction process.

Considering the limiting factors of FTDD during simulations, two groups can be distinguished. The first includes the RQC, QNN, RA, QPE, and QWalk circuits, for which execution time was the limiting factor. Within this group, two cases arise: for QPE and QWalk, FTDD could reach larger qubit counts than GTN in the absence of time constraints, whereas for RQC, RA, and QNN, GTN outperformed FTDD in both time and memory. The second group consists of the QFT, GHZ, and Graph circuits, where neither time nor memory limited FTDD; rather, the constraint was the maximum number of qubits available in the dataset we used. In this group, FTDD achieves substantially better performance than GTN in both metrics, and simulations could be extended to larger qubit counts if they were available.

We attempted to establish a correlation between the previously defined metrics and the computational performance of the simulators. However, our analysis reveals that none of these metrics consistently correlate with the runtime behavior exhibited by DD-based structures, contrasting with the results observed for matrix-based methods. This discrepancy arises because the complexity of DDs is not solely a function of the circuit’s topological structure or the tree-width of a given contraction order. Instead, the efficiency of DD-based simulation is heavily dependent on the algebraic regularity and redundancy inherent in the matrices encountered throughout the contraction process—features that topological metrics fail to capture. Consequently, while structural metrics provide a reliable proxy for the workload in traditional simulators, they prove insufficient for predicting the more volatile performance profile of DD-based frameworks. An example can be seen in Figure 6a, which provides a summary of the performance of the GTN simulator using the `sequential` ordering. As can be observed, when the circuits are ordered according to their execution time, the resulting ordering matches exactly the one induced by the *effort* metric shown previously in Figure 1. This indicates that *effort* serves as a reliable predictor of GTN’s runtime behavior. However, this correspondence does not hold for FTDD, as illustrated in Figure 6a. The performance of FTDD depends strongly on how effectively the structure of the underlying matrices can be exploited, resulting in a more irregular and less predictable runtime profile. Consequently, the *effort* metric fails to capture the dominant factors governing FTDD’s performance and therefore cannot be used to predict its behavior.

Fig. 4: Comparative between the tools GTN and FTDD and the contraction orders **sequential** and **cotengra** of the evolution of the memory used in the simulations in logarithmic scale measure in Kb respect the number of qubits of each circuit.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

This work has introduced a set of enhancements to the FTDD simulation tool, targeting its practical performance. First, we proposed a unified simulation interface that standardizes the execution workflow, thus improving usability and reproducibility. Second, we redesigned the internal `UniqueTable` and `ComputeTable` structures, preventing premature node deletion, enabling the safe reuse of nodes collected as dead, and introducing a heuristic mechanism that regulates table growth. These achieve more efficient memory utilization and substantially reduce memory overhead in large-scale simulations.

Our extensive experimental evaluation demonstrates the effectiveness of these improvements. The enhanced FTDD implementation exhibits a markedly superior memory profile compared with the original version, and in several circuit families—including QFT, GHZ, and Graph states—it achieves stable memory usage even as qubit counts increase. As a consequence, FTDD is able to simulate circuits with more than 120 qubits on a 2 TB machine, exceeding the capabilities of the matrix-based GTN simulator. These results position FTDD as a competitive alternative for large-scale quantum-circuit simulation, particularly in regimes where traditional tensor-network

Fig. 5: Comparative between the tools GTN and FTDD and the contraction orders **sequential** and **cotengra** of the evolution of the time used in the simulations in logarithmic scale measure in second respect the number of qubits of each circuit.

techniques fail due to exponential memory growth.

The comparative analysis further shows that FTDD and GTN exhibit complementary performance characteristics: FTDD excels for circuits with strong structural regularities, while GTN remains advantageous for circuits that generate highly irregular contraction patterns. Additionally, our study confirms that the *effort* metric provides an accurate predictor of GTN's runtime but does not capture the factors that dominate FTDD's behavior. This observation highlights the need for new metrics specifically tailored to DD simulation approaches.

Future work will explore advanced contraction-planning strategies tailored to DD-based structu-

res, extend the memory-management techniques to distributed memory and develop predictive metrics capable of characterising hybrid TN-DD behaviour. These directions are expected to further expand the applicability of FTDD.

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(a) Evolution of the time in seconds with logarithmic scale respect the number of qubits of the circuit for simulations done with GTN for each circuit group.

(b) Evolution of the time in seconds with logarithmic scale respect the number of qubits of the circuit for simulations done with FTDD for each circuit group.

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